

Digital tools and gamification in minoritised language contexts: (Un)availability, needs, and future perspectives

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Abstract

“RISE UP – Revitalising Languages and Safeguarding Cultural Diversity” is a HORIZON EUROPE project that aims to empower minoritised language communities in Europe. It focuses on five selected case study languages, namely Aranese, Aromanian, Burgenland Croatian, Cornish, and Seto. This paper highlights the project’s focus on methods for language revitalisation, with a particular emphasis on digital tools and services, and relates it to the development of the RISE UP digital toolkit. It draws on ethnographic research and preliminary data ($n=455$) of a survey that was adapted for the five language communities and translated into over 15 languages. Research data discussed in this article includes the exploration of the digital apps and services identified for the selected languages, how survey respondents receive some digital resources, and where they identify a lack of resources. Findings across the communities are compared and potential further needs are identified. Building onto this, the RISE UP digital toolkit is introduced and showcased as a comprehensive platform for learning and practising endangered languages, integrating gamification and user-friendly interfaces. It includes language learning games, language resources, a Linguistic Risk-Taking Tracker, and a community forum for user engagement. To conclude, the need for this toolkit is discussed.

Keywords: language revitalisation; minoritised language; digital resources; gamification.

1. Introduction

About half of the 7,000 languages used worldwide are considered endangered, meaning that they risk falling out of use and potentially facing extinction within a few decades. Revitalisation efforts are one response to this threat (Austin & Sallabank, 2011). According to Austin and Sallabank (2011), the promotion of language revitalisation “has the goal of maintaining living languages in their sociocultural contexts (i.e. in linguistic ecologies), and giving speakers the possibility to continue their use as well as passing them on to their descendants” (p. 22). The HORIZON EUROPE project “RISE UP – Revitalising Languages and Safeguarding Cultural Diversity” – on which this paper is based – also targets language revitalisation and aims to empower minoritised language communities by connecting relevant actors, identifying good practices that are already

available, and developing new methods using a multi-disciplinary approach.¹ The project focuses on five selected language communities in Europe, namely Aranese (Spain), Aromanian (Albania, Bulgaria, Greece, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia), Burgenland Croatian (Austria), Cornish (United Kingdom), and Seto (Estonia).

RISE UP is a Coordination and Support Action and has a project duration of 36 months (02/2023-01/2026). Eight partners from six European countries are involved in the project, namely MINDS & SPARKS GmbH, University of Tartu, University of Vienna, ESPRONCEDA Institute of Art & Culture, Youth of European Nationalities, NUROGAMES GmbH, School of Oriental and African Studies, and University of Roehampton.

In this paper, we focus on the aspect of digital tools and gamification in the context of the five RISE UP case study communities. Traditional efforts to revitalise languages are often associated with intergenerational transmission and how to foster it (Fishman, 1991). Other approaches highlight how important it is to enter new domains of language use and expand to new speakers (O'Rourke & Pujolar, 2013). When it comes to language safeguarding and revitalisation methods, the research conducted in the RISE UP project comprises three theoretical orientations (Cajka et al., 2024b; see also Cajka et al., 2024a)²:

- A linguistic ecology approach: According to Mühlhäusler (2018), taking an ecological approach to language revitalisation involves the creation of a sustainable future for languages and varieties. Revitalisation efforts encompass maintaining linguistic diversity, restoring functional connections between different languages and varieties, and embedding them within meaningful cultural, economic, and ecological contexts.
- An interest in language users: New speakers are conceptualised as “individuals who put their energy and effort into learning and using a minoritised language, be they originally labelled “traditional” speakers with partial competence, newcomers, or any other members of the communities” (Cajka et al., 2024b, p. 12).
- A usage-based approach to language learning: Teaching, learning, and using languages are conceptualised as closely linked (Ellis, 2015).

As new language users are essential for the vitality of a language and face-to-face opportunities for target language use are often scarce in minoritised language contexts, digital opportunities can play a very important role in the learning and use of an endangered language. In this sense, CALL (Computer-Assisted Language Learning) seems to be particularly important for minoritised languages. CALL can provide them with access to resources that might otherwise be not available (Ward, 2015). In our understanding of a usage-based approach to language learning, any interaction with a digital tool, app, or service in the minoritised language can be an opportunity for language learning and can therefore be associated with CALL. However, there are concerns about a ‘digital divide’, meaning that minoritised languages’ access to and use of technologies compared to dominant languages is characterized by an imbalance (UNESCO, 2022, p. 289). This paper explores which digital apps and services for the five selected languages can be identified, how respondents to the RISE UP questionnaire survey receive some digital resources, and where they identify a lack of resources. The findings across the five case studies are compared, initial conclusions are drawn, and further needs regarding digital resources are discussed. Building on these preliminary results, we then introduce the RISE UP digital toolkit and conclude with a discussion of the need for it.

2. Method

The data discussed in this paper was collected through ethnographic research (including site visits, meetings with community contacts, and desk research online, happening in a recursive process over several months) as well as

¹ For more information, please visit the project website www.riseupproject.eu.

² The project deliverable (Cajka et al., 2024b) providing more in-depth information will be published here: <https://www.riseupproject.eu/about/>

an online questionnaire survey among the five RISE UP case study communities, hosted on Microsoft Forms. It was adapted for each of the case study communities and then translated into over 15 language varieties (see Cajka et al., 2024a and 2024b for more information). All of this happened in a joint effort of the RISE UP consortium.

The data presented in this paper was accessed in March 2024 and is preliminary, as the survey was still ongoing at that time. It comprises 455 responses and was analysed using descriptive statistics. It is important to note that the data provides initial insights into the perceptions of the survey respondents, but it is not representative of the entire case study communities. As the data is still preliminary, the number of responses for the five language communities varies. In order to contextualise the data, we present a brief overview of the demographic characteristics of the respondents in each of the case study communities.

Aranese. A total of eight participants completed the questionnaire. The majority of respondents indicated an age between 30 and 49 years. One respondent reported to be between 18 and 29; two assigned themselves to the age category of 50 to 69 years. Four respondents identified as male, three as female, and one person preferred not to disclose their gender. All survey respondents reported having completed higher education (e.g., university, college).

Aromanian. 228 persons responded to the survey. Almost 40% of the participants indicated that they are between 30 and 49 years old, while over a third of them (35.5%) stated that they are between 50 and 69 years old. 8.3% of respondents reported to be 70 or older, and approximately 16% reported to be under the age of 30 (with 14.9% in the 18-29 age range and 1.3% between the ages of 10 and 17). The gender distribution was relatively balanced, with 53.9% identifying as male and 44.7% as female. One respondent indicated to be non-binary and two preferred not to disclose their gender. The majority of respondents (86.8%) have reportedly completed higher education. 10.1% indicated secondary school to be the highest education they have completed. Six individuals reported vocational training and one person reported primary/elementary school as their highest completed education.

Burgenland Croatian. The questionnaire was completed by a total of 115 people. With regard to age, those reportedly aged between 30 and 49 account for the largest proportion with 36.5%. This is followed by the age group of 50 to 69 with 27%. 26.1% indicated to be aged between 18 and 29, and 10.4% of the respondents reported being 70 years of age or older. 60% of the respondents identified as female, 36.5% as male. A further 3.5% of respondents preferred not to disclose their gender. In terms of the highest completed education, almost three quarters (74.8%) of the respondents have reportedly completed higher education. The remaining quarter is distributed as follows: 16.5% indicated that they have completed secondary school, 7% stated that they have completed vocational training and two people selected the 'Other' option.

Cornish. 37 questionnaires were completed for Cornish. More than half of the respondents (54.1%) were reportedly aged between 50 and 69 years. The age group between 30 and 49 constitutes 27% of the sample. 16.2% of respondents indicated to be between 18 and 29 years old, while 2.7% stated to be aged 70 or above. The majority (54.1%) identified as male, 35.1% as female. A further 5.4% of respondents identified as non-binary and 5.4% preferred not to disclose their gender. The majority of respondents have reportedly completed higher education (83.8%). 10.8% indicated that the highest level of education they have completed was secondary school and 5.4% reported having completed vocational training.

Seto. A total of 67 persons completed the survey for Seto. The majority of respondents reported to be 50 years and older, with 50.7% in the 50-69 age group and 7.5% in the 70-or-older age group. 26.9% indicated to be between 30 and 49 years old, 9% stated to be in the 18-29 age group, and 6% responded to be aged between 10 and 17. The majority of participants (56.7%) identified as female, 40.3% as male. 3% decided not to disclose their gender. In terms of the highest level of education completed, 64.2% of respondents indicated higher education, 13.4% vocational training, and 11.9% secondary school. 6% indicated primary/elementary school as the highest education they have completed, while 4.5% selected the 'Other' option.

3. Preliminary results

3.1. Identified digital apps and services³ for the five case study communities⁴

As part of the research in RISE UP, already available resources were identified with regard to the five case study communities (Cajka et al., 2024a). In this context, the term ‘resources’ encompasses everything “that requires the active or passive use of the minoritised language. I.e., people have to use the minoritised language to interact with the respective resource or engage in the respective activity.” (Cajka et al., 2024a, p. 15). This paper highlights the findings regarding digital apps and services, relates them to survey data and the development of the RISE UP digital toolkit. The lists of digital apps and services identified for the five selected case study communities that we refer to in this paper can be found in Cajka et al. (2024a, pp. 36-73). They are based on our initial research and are still a work in progress. These lists do not claim to be exhaustive but will expand as the project progresses. A digital version of the current list of identified resources is available under this link: <https://www.riseupproject.eu/resources/>. It provides an opportunity for users to add resources that will contribute to the growth of the list.

In general, there seem to be very few digital apps and services for the five selected languages. Online dictionaries are available for all of them, but otherwise the resources identified vary widely between the five communities.

The largest number and broadest range of resources – though still very small compared to the numbers of resources available for majority languages such as English or German – were identified for Cornish. These included various online learning resources (such as audio courses or language learning apps), games (such as “Kerdle”, the Cornish version of Wordle) and digital services (such as autocorrect for Cornish).

With regards to Burgenland Croatian, it was interesting to see that of the four resources identified, two were related to music. The web application “Pjesmio” allows users to collect, share, and present song lyrics, and “Zajačimo si” is a songbook app of popular Croatian folk and pop songs.

For Aromanian, an online library was identified, as well as some online offerings explicitly related to language learning, such as an online learning platform, online learning resources, or online courses. With regards to Aranese, we identified a translation tool and various online dictionaries. Seto was the case study community with the least number of digital apps and services identified (two online dictionaries).

3.2. Reception of specific resources

To find out more about respondents’ general perceptions of specific resources, we listed several resources (which had already been identified at the time the questionnaire was designed) and asked respondents how important they found them. They were able to respond on a 5-point scale from ‘extremely important [5]’ to ‘not at all important [1]’ and the alternative option ‘I don’t know this resource [0]’.

With regards to Aranese, most of the online resources listed, except for one (which was also unknown to 37.5% of the respondents), were considered (extremely) important by the majority of respondents. Responses to the Aromanian questionnaire were even more straightforward, with each resource listed being considered (extremely) important by at least 68% of the respondents. In the case of Seto, the two online dictionaries listed were perceived to be (extremely) important by a high percentage of respondents (with 91% and 88.1% ranking them as (extremely) important).

³ Under digital apps and services, we understand “Phone apps in/for the case study language / the case study community (e.g. online dictionaries), and digital tools/services available in the case study language, such as Wikipedia, machine translation, computer operating systems, mobile phone software, chatbots, games for PC/phone.” (Cajka et al., 2024a, p. 19). More information on this categorisation and its development can be found in Cajka et al. (2024a).

⁴ This and more findings regarding the resources identified for the five RISE UP case study communities have been published in Cajka et al. (2024a).

For Burgenland Croatian, the online dictionary “rječnik.at” had the highest percentage of respondents considering it (extremely) important (86.1%). For all the other resources listed, far more respondents perceived them to be (extremely) important than not (at all) important, but it was noticeable that they were unknown to a considerable number of participants.

The results for Cornish were similar to those for Burgenland Croatian. In general, more respondents perceived the listed resources to be (extremely) important than not (at all) important. For the option “Learning platforms (e.g. Go Cornish or SaySomethingInCornish)”, 86.5% of the respondents indicated that they find it (extremely) important. The “Online Cornish Dictionary” received an even higher rating, with 94.6% of respondents considering it (extremely) important. The digital game “Kerdle” elicited more divergent responses, with 29.7% of respondents perceiving it as (extremely) important and 18.9% perceiving it as not (at all) important. Similarly to Burgenland Croatian, some listed resources had a considerable number of respondents choosing the ‘I don’t know this resource [0]’ option.

3.3. Perceived lack of resources

To explore the areas in which respondents perceive resources in the respective language to be most lacking, we provided a list of areas (‘Media’, ‘Events’, ‘Literature and non-fiction works’, ‘Music’, ‘Facilities and services’, ‘Competitions/awards’, ‘Further resources/offering’, ‘Digital services’, ‘In no area’) and an open-ended ‘Others’ option. Respondents were allowed to select as many options as they found appropriate.

‘Digital services’ was one of the top three areas where resources were reported to lack the most for Aranese and Aromanian. For Burgenland Croatian, it was even chosen most frequently as an area where resources for Burgenland Croatian lack the most. Interestingly, ‘Media’, ‘Literature and non-fiction works’ and ‘Facilities and services’ ranked as the top three areas where resources in the language lacked reportedly the most for Cornish. ‘Digital services’ was ranked fourth, along with the ‘Events’ category. For Seto, ‘Digital services’ ranked fifth out of 10. The areas that were perceived to lack the most for Seto resources were the same as for Cornish: ‘Media’, ‘Literature and non-fiction works’ and ‘Facilities and services’.

Figure 1. Percentages of respondents who indicated that ‘Digital services’ were an area where resources for the respective language lack the most

To gain further insights, we compared the percentage of respondents who identified ‘Digital services’ as an area where resources for their respective language lack the most from the five respective language communities. This is illustrated in the figure above. Despite the differences between the case study communities in terms of their

number of respondents, there was a considerable number of participants who identified ‘Digital services’ as an area where resources for the respective language lack the most. For four out of five communities (Aranese, Aromanian, Burgenland Croatian, and Cornish) more than 50% of the respondents ticked this option. For Seto, however, only 26.9% indicated that ‘Digital services’ was an area where Seto resources lack the most.

4. Discussion

In the previous section, we discussed preliminary results with regards to which digital apps and services for the five selected languages could be identified, how respondents to the RISE UP questionnaire survey received some digital resources, and where they identified a lack of resources.

The findings illustrate that the digital apps and services available in the five RISE UP case study communities are notably scarce, even though some of them appear to be better equipped than others, as in the case of Cornish. Online dictionaries are available in all five communities and can therefore be considered a standard tool. Otherwise, the lack of resources in the digital sphere is evident, which ties in with the digital divide mentioned by UNESCO (2022). For three of the five case study communities we could not identify any digital resources explicitly for language learning, revealing a gap in this respect. While some digital language learning tools were found for Cornish and Aromanian, there may be room for more.

A lack of resources for the five minoritised languages is also suggested by the preliminary survey results. For Aranese, Aromanian, and Burgenland Croatian, ‘Digital services’ ranked in the top three areas where resources for the respective case study community language lack the most. But also other areas such as ‘Media’ or ‘Literature and non-fiction works’ ranked frequently among these top three areas, suggesting a wide-ranging need for resources in these minoritised languages. However, when comparing the percentages of respondents who identified ‘Digital services’ as an area where resources in the respective language lack the most, it was found that in four out of five case study communities, over 50% of respondents selected ‘Digital services’. These preliminary findings indicate that only the Seto respondents exhibited a comparatively lower need in the digital sphere, with approximately a quarter of respondents who selected ‘Digital services’ as an area where Seto resources lack the most. One explanation for this, and also for the fact that ‘Digital services’ did not rank in the top three categories where Seto resources lack the most, may be that more than 57% of the respondents were 50 years or older. However, more statistical analyses are needed to explore this further.

The findings regarding the reception of specific resources show that there were more respondents who considered most of the digital resources listed in their respective version of the questionnaire to be (extremely) important than respondents who considered them to be not (at all) important. For Burgenland Croatian and Cornish, it was particularly noticeable that some of the resources are unknown to a considerable number of respondents. With regards to Burgenland Croatian, these findings may be due to the demographics of the respondents, as only about a quarter of them reported to be under the age of 30, or to a lack of advertisement for these resources (see Cajka et al., 2024b, for more details on the aspect of advertisement regarding language revitalisation resources). In any case, unknown resources are unfortunate as they cannot fulfil their full potential if they are not well known in the respective community (see Cajka et al., 2024b, for further explanations in this regard).

Given that these results are based on preliminary data and that the survey data was analysed with descriptive statistics, further detailed analyses of the final survey data combined with more in-depth qualitative and/or ethnographic data are required to gain a more nuanced understanding of the needs of the five selected language communities.

5. The RISE UP digital toolkit

The RISE UP digital toolkit represents a new perspective in the efforts to revitalise and safeguard endangered languages within Europe (Shekhawat, 2024). This comprehensive platform is designed to support the learning, practice, and revitalisation of minoritised languages through a blend of advanced technologies and community-

driven features. By integrating gamification and user-friendly interfaces, the toolkit aims to create an engaging and immersive experience for users, bridging the gap between traditional language learning methods and modern digital solutions. The key features of the app are:

1. **Language Learning Games.** The toolkit includes a variety of language learning games tailored to each of the five case study languages: Aranese, Aromanian, Burgenland Croatian, Cornish, and Seto. These games are not only educational but also culturally informative, providing insights into the history, traditions, and values of each community. By making learning fun and interactive, the games encourage consistent practice and deeper engagement with the language. The design of the lesson plan includes thematic sections, that are split up into several units. Each unit starts with an authentic text (i.e. mostly a dialogue) that is based on daily interactions. This is followed by several exercises that focus on chunk learning, sentence structure, grammar, and vocabulary. The structure of the exercises is designed to facilitate any verified and approved user to create a language course for the application.
2. **Digital Resources.** To further aid language learners, the toolkit can offer dictionaries and thesauruses for each language. These resources are essential for expanding vocabulary and understanding language nuances, making them valuable tools for both new and experienced learners.
3. **Linguistic Risk-Taking Tracker.** An innovative feature of the RISE UP toolkit is the Linguistic Risk-Taking Tracker. It adapts the concept of Linguistic Risk-Taking (Cajka et al., 2023; Roodi & Slavkov, 2022; Slavkov & Sérór, 2019) for a minoritised language learning application. This tool encourages users to practice the language in real-life situations, promoting confidence and proficiency. By tracking the progress of the user and rewarding each linguistic risk with in-app reward points and badges, the toolkit motivates users to step out of their comfort zones and actively use the language in their daily lives.
4. **Community Forum.** Community engagement is a cornerstone of the RISE UP digital toolkit. The integrated forum allows users to connect, share experiences, create events, and participate in discussions. This feature fosters a supportive network of language learners and more proficient language users, enhancing the sense of community and shared purpose among users, which increases the engagement and promotes collective motivation towards language usage.

Gamification plays a pivotal role in the RISE UP digital toolkit, making language learning more engaging and rewarding. The toolkit incorporates several gamification techniques that cater to the diverse needs of its users:

1. **Progression Levels and Points System.** Users can advance through various levels that reflect their mastery of the language, earning points for completing lessons and challenges. This system provides a clear sense of progress and achievement, motivating users to continue their learning journey.
2. **Badges and Achievements.** Badges are awarded for specific accomplishments, such as mastering key vocabulary. These visual markers of success not only recognise user efforts but also add an element of fun and competition.
3. **Daily and Weekly Challenges.** Time-bound challenges encourage regular engagement with the language. These challenges can range from vocabulary exercises to quizzes, offering extra points and rewards upon completion.
4. **Leaderboards and Social Interaction.** Leaderboards create a sense of friendly competition, while social interaction features such as peer-to-peer communication and group challenges promote collaboration and community building.

The app will be available for iOS and Android. A web platform will also allow verified and approved users to create language courses accessible to all app users for that language.

Figure 2. Designs of the RISE UP Digital toolkit v1

6. Conclusion: The need for a digital toolkit

Preliminary data discussed in this paper suggests a considerable lack of resources in the selected language communities. Current digital services, media, and literature – but also other resources for these languages – are notably lacking, creating barriers to effective language learning, language use, and revitalisation. For instance, in the Aranese community, there is a perceived shortage of digital services despite the high importance placed on most of such resources by the survey respondents. Similarly, the preliminary findings for Aromanian suggest a need for more resources with regards to media, digital services, and literature – resources that are crucial for sustaining and promoting the language. The Burgenland Croatian and Seto community, too, appear to have limited access to essential digital resources in their languages, making it difficult to support minoritised language use and learning effectively. While Cornish has the most digital apps and services identified compared to the other four languages, it is still far less than what is available for majority languages.

We suggest the RISE UP digital toolkit as an answer to the multiple challenges for minoritised languages in a globalised and digitalised world. The toolkit aims to fill these gaps by providing a comprehensive suite of digital resources tailored to the specific needs of these communities. It offers language learning games, which are not only educational but also engaging, making the process of learning more interactive and enjoyable. This is a significant improvement over current resources, which often lack interactive and gamified elements that can motivate learners. Additionally, the toolkit aims to include a comprehensive digital dictionary and thesaurus, as they are paramount to any language and their perceived importance is also mirrored in the survey responses.

Another innovative feature of the RISE UP toolkit is the Linguistic Risk-Taking Tracker, which encourages users to practise the language in real-life situations. By tracking and rewarding users' efforts to use the language in various contexts, the toolkit promotes active engagement and practical application of language skills. This feature is particularly important in minoritised language contexts, where opportunities for face-to-face language use can be scarce.

Furthermore, the toolkit aims to foster community engagement through its integrated forum, a feature that might be used on social media, but is not widely available in current digital resources. This forum allows users to connect, share experiences, create events, and participate in discussions, building a supportive network of language learners and speakers. This community aspect is vital for sustaining language use and fostering a sense of belonging among users. By providing a platform for social interaction and community building, the toolkit addresses the isolation that many minoritised language speakers might experience, offering a space for mutual support and collaboration.

In this paper, we have discussed the RISE UP digital toolkit being developed for the five selected language communities Aranese, Aromanian, Burgenland Croatian, Cornish, and Seto. The goal is, however, that the structure behind it can be adapted to minoritised languages beyond these five communities, potentially opening up future perspectives for language revitalisation in the digital sphere.

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